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Harwell TCCON Site

Accreditation application report V1.3

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1. Introduction

The Science & Technology Facilities Council (STFC) is one of seven research councils comprising UK Research & Innovation (UKRI), a body working in partnership with universities, agencies and government to support the UK research effort. STFC, in contrast to other research councils, runs major science & technology programmes using its own research capability in support of major UK physical and life science facilities.

The Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) is a public-sector laboratory owned and operated by STFC and located near the village of Harwell in south-eastern England. RAL Space is one of the departments in the Laboratory and facilitates interaction between UK government, the space industry and academic institutions in world-leading research and technology development, space test facilities and instrument & mission design.

Within RAL Space, the Spectroscopy Group has unique expertise in molecular spectroscopy and high-resolution atmospheric sounding. Its activity covers spectroscopic instrument concept and design, high-resolution laboratory reference spectroscopy, spectroscopic modelling, and development and validation of prototype spectroscopic instruments for field deployment.

In recent years, funded by RAL Space and the UK National Centre for Earth Observation, the Spectroscopy Group has developed a prospective TCCON site using one of its IFS 120/5 HR, coupled to an in-house solar tracker, to recording solar zenith occultation transmission spectra according to the protocol established by the TCCON network. In this process, the instrumental performance requirements stipulated by the TCCON community have been successively addressed, with corrective action being taken where necessary. Spectroscopy Group has also developed in-house capability with the GGG2020 retrieval software, the ongoing output of which will contribute to validation of overall installation performance.

The installation now fulfils all the technical requirements and measurements are made routinely as sky conditions allow. The RAL Spectroscopy Group would therefore like to request accreditation for the Harwell instrument as a provisional TCCON site; this document provides the supporting background information, instrument performance metrics and characteristics of retrievals performed to date.

2. Site description

The Harwell TCCON installation is sited at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, some 6 km SW of the town of Didcot in Oxfordshire, UK. The site has coordinates 51.571° N, 1.315° W and lies 129 m AMSL on the southern perimeter of the RAL science & technology complex with a southerly view over predominantly arable farmland.

Didcot has an estimated population 30,000 in 2019 with a built-up area of ~10 km². Didcot B power station, with its 1.4 GW combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) plant fuelled by natural gas, represents a potential local emissions source 6.5 km from the Harwell site on a bearing of 30°. The height of the exhaust gas chimney is ~80 m. Fig. 2.1 shows the location of the Didcot B exhaust stack in relation to the Harwell site to the south-west (courtesy Google Earth). Also shown is a wind rose taken from the Global Wind Atlas (<https://globalwindatlas.info/>) for the village of Chilton, some 1.2 km east of the Harwell site. The relative frequency of wind directions in the 30 ° sector in which the Didcot B fume stack lies is ~ 5%.

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Most of the time, the Harwell site will not see the plume from the gas station transported into its field of view. However, a few occurrences could happen and it would be very interesting to analyse the corresponding data together with a transport model.

Fig. 2.1 : Location of the Harwell site relative to the nearby Didcot B CCGT power station. Inset : wind rose for Chilton village, approximately 1 km east of the Harwell site.

Fig. 2.2 shows an aerial view (courtesy Google Earth) of the site surroundings. The RAL campus is seen at the top of the frame, with the solar tracker location indicated by the red circle. Figs. 2.3a and 2.3b show the astronomical dome housing the solar tracker, which directs the solar radiation to the IFS spectrometer in the adjacent laboratory, and a close-up of the set of meteorological sensors located next to the dome.

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Fig. 2.2: RAL campus and the TCCON installation in relation to its surroundings to the south.

Fig. 2.3a: The tracker dome and meteorological sensors outside the IFS laboratory.

The field of view of the solar tracker in its current location is approximately between 70° and 250° azimuth, resulting in a significant curtailment of measurement opportunity in the summer months. Work is currently under way to relocate the tracker to a rooftop location with unrestricted line-of-sight to the sun over the entire year, and the IFS120/5 to a laboratory below, into which the solar beam will be directed by the tracker. Completion of the work is expected by summer 2021.

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Fig. 2.3b: The set of meteorological sensors.

3. TCCON requirements & norms

The TCCON network has evolved to become the international reference ground-based remote sounding infrastructure to validate and augment the global GHG observing system, which places stringent requirements on the accuracy of its retrieved products, most notably CO₂ (accuracy < 0.5 ppm). These requirements for the retrieved products propagate into the end-to-end processor and instrumental requirements. The primary instrumental requirements as determined by the TCCON community over the last 20 years are listed in Table 3.1. In addition, to ensure individual TCCON sites operate as similarly as possible, a number of recommendations, norms or typical instrumental values have been established, which are listed in Table 3.2 together with an indication of the degree of compliance of the Harwell site.

Parameters	Range or limit	Units	Fulfilled?
Operating spectral range	< 4000 - 9000	cm ⁻¹	Y
Interferometer optical path difference	≥ 45	cm	Y
Phase resolution	≤ 1	cm ⁻¹	Y
Tracker pointing precision	< 1 (0.2 ideal)	mrad	Y (Y)
Surface pressure error	< 0.3	mbar	Y
Surface temperature error	< 1	K	Y
Zero Path Difference crossing time accuracy	< 1	s	Y
Laser sampling error	< 2.4 x 10 ⁻⁴	sample step	Y
Monthly HCl reference spectrum SNR	> 2500		Y
Modulation efficiency variation over OPD	< 5	%	Y
Phase error	Understood to be ± 5	mrad	Partial

Table 3.1: List of TCCON accreditation requirements.

Parameters	Recommendation or norm	Units	Fulfilled?
Fourier Transform Spectrometer	Bruker IFS12X series		Y
GHG band SNR (SWIR)	750		Y
O ₂ band SNR (760 nm)	200		Y
Acquisition time per spectrum pair	150	s	Y
Detector signal coupling	DC		Y
Entrance stop aperture	1	mm	Y

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Folding limits	0, 15798	cm ⁻¹	Y
Scanner velocity equivalent to :	10	kHz	Y
Low/high-pass filter	10 / 0	kHz	Y
Phase correction	Mertz		Y
Apodisation	Boxcar		Y

Table 3.2: List of TCCON recommendations or norms.

Sections 4 and 5 demonstrate where necessary how the Harwell installation conforms to the requirements of Table 3.1 and the norms of Table 3.2 respectively.

4. Installation conformance to requirements

Section 4 presents evidence of conformance of the Harwell site's installation to the strict requirements of TCCON participation.

4.1. Spectral range

The minimum TCCON requirement is for SWIR spectral coverage over the range 4000-9000 cm⁻¹, which is met by use of an extended range thermoelectrically-cooled InGaAs detector (xInGaAs) with sensitivity range ~ 4000-12000 cm⁻¹. The CaF₂ beamsplitter readily accommodates the lower wavelength limit of 4000 cm⁻¹. In addition, the Harwell system incorporates a Si detector in dual-channel configuration, allowing simultaneous acquisition in the spectral region 9000-16000 cm⁻¹. A dichroic mirror with 50% transmission at ~ 11500 cm⁻¹ is used to separate radiation for the two channels. For illustration, Fig. 4.1 shows relevant regions of the two spectral channels recorded around 11:00 UTC on 4th November 2020. The value of the additional spectral channel lies in the acquisition of the O₂ A-band around 769 nm (13000 cm⁻¹) which is used to derive a value for the air column coincident with the SWIR spectrum.

Fig. 4.1: Illustrative spectra recorded by the Harwell instrument as displayed in the Opus interface using the dual-detector configuration.

4.2. OPD & phase resolution

The IFS120/5 HR (S/N GI003092) has a maximum OPD of ~ 6 metres (resolution 0.0015 cm⁻¹ as per Bruker definition) and so easily meets the TCCON OPD requirement. The 1 cm⁻¹ phase resolution is also readily achieved.

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The quality of instrumental optical alignment as assessed through a measurement of ILS is addressed in Section 4.8.

4.3. Solar tracker pointing precision

The four-quadrant detector solar tracker in place at the beginning of the TCCON station development was found to have a largely insufficient pointing accuracy, with deviations over a 1-hour period of up to 1.5 mrad. In addition, during partially cloudy conditions, the tracker frequently lost its lock and, without a means of passive tracking using celestial coordinate calculation, was unable to re-locate the sun to continue tracking. Furthermore, interferograms were found to be perturbed by signal intensity fluctuations stemming from tracker electro-mechanical instabilities with the potential to generate spectral artefacts.

An alternative tracker concept (the 'camtracker') has been developed at Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie and commercialised for TCCON application by Bruker. In discussion with Bruker, it was established that their solution could not be implemented as a turnkey solution owing to incompatibilities between current Bruker interferometer compartments and our IFS120/5, whose shell was built in the 1990s and later refurbished to IFS125 standards. Concerns expressed by many TCCON partners regarding the responsiveness of the Bruker maintenance for their tracker was also a decisive factor. Given RAL Space Spectroscopy Group experience and success in designing, building and operating smaller alt-azimuth trackers based on active camera tracking, it was decided to implement a custom solution.

Fig. 4.2 shows the concept of the alt-azimuth tracker, in which the first mirror (accommodating solar elevation) and the entire housing (accommodating solar azimuth) are mounted on precision rotation stages allowing fine control of the line-of-sight elevation and azimuth. Also shown in Fig. 4.2 is the in-house tracker after completion, deployed in its astronomical dome.

Fig. 4.2: Left : Schematic of the alt-azimuth tracker concept. Right : The RAL solar tracker installed in the astronomical dome.

The tracker is designed using gold coated elliptical mirrors (13.0 cm × 18.4 cm) producing a 13-cm diameter beam to allow an extended flexibility on the distance between the spectrometer input and tracker (the current distance being 7 m). The rotation stages controlling the elevation and azimuth motions have an angular resolution of 0.87 and 0.017 μ rad, respectively.

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In addition to the solar tracker hardware, the cam-tracking system and the control software was developed. The purpose of this system is to ensure that the solar disk at the input of the spectrometer is always co-aligned to the spectrometer entrance aperture. A CMOS camera captures the sun disk image on the aperture wheel. From these images, feedback to the tracker is generated and sent to the rotation stages. A typical image can be seen in the right-hand panel of the LabVIEW camtracker interface shown in Fig. 4.3. In addition to the active cam-tracking, the software automatically switches to passive mode Earth rotation compensation based on celestial coordinates when active tracking is impeded.

Fig. 4.3: Left, Interferometer source chamber showing CMOS camera for monitoring the image of the solar disc. Right, the RAL custom camtracker LabVIEW interface.

As an example, Fig. 4.4 shows the time series of the active tracking corrections applied to each of the azimuth and elevation rotation stages for the 20-minute period from 11:45 on 9th March 2021, together with the histogram of the de-trended pointing correction magnitude. The tracker pointing precision (equated to the correction magnitude) lies within the range of ~ 0.1 mrad, with mean 0.031 ± 0.018 mrad, which is within the ideal criterion of ≤ 0.2 mrad.

Fig. 4.4: Time series and histogram of the active solar tracker pointing correction characteristics for a 20-minute period of operation on 9th March 2021.

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4.4. Surface temperature & pressure measurements

Surface temperature, pressure and relative humidity are measured continuously at the tracker location by a Vaisala PTU307 unit, logged as 1-minute averages and saved daily. An example of a day's logged data is shown in Fig. 4.5.

Fig. 4.5: Pressure, temperature and relative humidity (RH) recorded by the Vaisala unit at the tracker location for 26th February 2021.

Data are measured with accuracies of 0.2 °C, 0.2 hPa and 1% for temperature, pressure and relative humidity respectively. The Vaisala unit is, however, due for recalibration.

4.5. Zero path difference (ZPD) crossing accuracy

Time stamping

Interferograms are recorded using Opus; the Opus file time stamp is used to calculate the ZPD crossing time according to a [technical note](#) on the TCCON Wiki. The PC running Opus is linked to a TimeTools T100 GPS time server with a quoted clock accuracy of 3 μs. The PC clock therefore meets the required timing accuracy of 1 second. However, our understanding is that the Opus file time stamp is derived from the IFS control unit clock, not the PC clock. The control unit clock is updated at a user-selectable interval by Opus, currently set at 1 hour for our system. Provided any drift between control unit clock and PC clock is less than one 1 second per hour, therefore, the Harwell data are TCCON-compliant; however, that remains an assumption. We have contacted Bruker to ask how to interrogate the control unit clock directly, and are awaiting a response.

Correction of Bruker IFS firmware bug affecting time stamping accuracy

Inspection of the Harwell IFS120/5 Opus file metadata parameters shows an inconsistency in the way the interferogram peak locations for forward and backward scans are stored for the two detector channels. Dave Pollard (TCCON, Lauder, New Zealand) has confirmed that the inconsistency arises from the version 2.485 of the Bruker IFS125 firmware, which is common to the Harwell and Lauder (and

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possibly other) site instruments. With this particular firmware, the parameter storing the peak location of the forward scan for the second (the InGaAs) detector is incompatible with the spectral processing algorithm, and not time-stamped properly.

This parameter is listed in the Opus metadata as 'Peak location 2nd channel' and referred to as P2L in Bruker's Opus reference manual. The Lauder team found that this inconsistency generates a timing error of some tens of seconds when used by the GGG2020 Fortran routine *create_runlog* to calculate the ZPD time, which in turn results in a forward-backward bias in xLuft mostly prominent at large solar zenith angles. The 'fix' adopted by the Lauder team is to set the P2L parameter equal to the corresponding parameter for the first detector channel (denoted PKL), so that a similar convention for specifying peak locations is used for both detector channels. The fix is implemented by constructing a new Opus file from the original with a corrected P2L peak location before processing the data with I2S. Dave Pollard offered to share the fix in the form of a Python script; Stamatia Doniki (RAL) and Alex Geddes (NIWA) have worked on updating the script from Python 2 to Python 3, which can be used either as a stand-alone script or integrated into the wider Opus file processing chain. All data presented later in section 6 have been generated using this fix. The effect of the fix on xLuft is illustrated in Figure 4.6 for four selected days in the span from September 2020 - February 2021. xLuft for forward and backward scans without the 'fix' are shown in black and red diamonds respectively (left hand side) ; for the 'fixed' data, forward and backward scan xLuft values are shown in black and red crosses respectively (right hand side).

In three cases shown in Figure 4.6 (24 Sept 2020, 04 Nov 2020, and 27 Feb 2021) the xLuft bias is suppressed. The 24 Dec 2020 measurement is not improved, suggesting that in this particular case other issues were responsible for the backward/forward bias. For this measurement, one should note that the temporal record is shorter and centred at local noon anyway, where the forward/backward bias is insignificant.

Fig. 4.6 : Effect of the Lauder peak location 'fix' on Harwell data for selected days across the winter period. The left- and right-hand plots result from 'raw' and 'fixed' Opus files respectively.

4.6. Laser sampling error

The Harwell IFS120/5 was fitted with the LSB board developed for TCCON for ghost suppression in January 2020 as part of a service visit by Gregor Surawicz. Using a narrow-band filter at 6060 cm^{-1} he achieved a ghost-parent suppression ration of $\sim 5 \times 10^{-5}$ and activated the XSM firmware correction. In addition, the ghost suppression flag is set in I2S.

Laser sampling errors have been recovered from the output of I2S applied to the set of recorded data described later in Section 6. The results are compared to the requirement for a sampling error less than 2.4×10^{-4} of a sample step as shown in Fig. 4.7.

Fig. 4.7: Laser sampling errors from the output of I2S applied to a set of data recorded over the period September 2020 – March 2021.

4.7. Instrument lineshape function

The Harwell instrument is equipped with an externally mounted TCCON HCl cell (ID 49) illuminated with a 50 W tungsten-halogen source. Fig. 4.8 shows how a removable mirror used to direct the solar beam from the tracker can be temporarily removed to allow the HCl cell source beam to enter the interferometer via the same focusing optic as the solar beam; HCl spectra are then recorded separately from atmospheric transmission spectra. A black anodised Al housing prevents illumination of the cell's glass walls by the W-halogen lamp that might otherwise lead to heating of the cell contents above ambient temperature.

Fig. 4.8 : Optical layout for the HCl calibration cell and source.

HCl cell spectra are currently averaged over 100 forward-backward scan pairs, using AC detector coupling to improve dynamic range, to achieve an SNR of ~ 3000 as calculated from the noise RMS in the out-of-band region 2500-3000 cm^{-1} and the background spectrum intensity at 5740 cm^{-1} . Opus files are then processed by I2S prior to input to Linefit version 14.5. Initial tuning of the fit constraints was carried

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out with advice kindly provided by Frank Hase. Fig. 4.9 shows an example of a spectrum around the HCL line at 5739.25 cm^{-1} , the ILS estimated using Linefit (13-microwindow model) and the residual.

Fig. 4.9 : Experimental absorption spectrum, ILS derived using Linefit, and residual from the HCL calibration cell.

On 23rd June 2021 the HCL cell was repositioned into the InGaAs detector beam path inside the IFS sample chamber to allow direct lineshape calibration of the optical path taken by solar radiation (see Fig. 4.10). The in situ positioning of the cell is now the default for all solar spectrum acquisition, in line with current TCCON practice. The cell may be periodically moved to its previous external position to allow the external lineshape calibration using the tungsten source required under the TCCON protocol. The switch in cell position is readily and reliably achieved using magnetic kinematic mounts.

Fig. 4.10 : The in situ HCL lineshape calibration cell placed in the InGaAs detector beam path.

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4.8. Modulation efficiency and phase error

HCl cell spectra have been recorded as above from September 2020 to April 2021 (the time of writing) at approximately monthly intervals and processed with Linefit to retrieve the modulation efficiency (ME) and phase error (PE) as a function of OPD, as a diagnostic for the quality of the IFS 120/5 alignment. Fig. 4.11 shows representative results as a function of OPD; Fig. 4.12 shows summary data for the set of 6 spectra, indicating the extrema of ME and PE for each spectrum over the OPD range. The analysis was carried out on both components of a forward-backward scan. In the ME plot, the dashed line indicates the 95% level below which the modulation efficiency should not fall. In the phase error plot, the dashed lines indicate the range of ~ 0.01 radian within which the phase error should fall.

The corresponding HCl column scaling factors are shown in Fig. 4.13.

Fig. 4.11 : Modulation efficiency (ME) and phase error (PE) as a function of optical path difference (OPD) for the data of 23 March 2021.

Fig. 4.12 : Extrema of modulation efficiency and phase error derived from HCl cell spectra covering the period of Sept 2020 to Mar 2021.

Fig. 4.13 : Retrieved scaling factor in units of HCl cell column over the 6-month period.

4.9. Detector non-linearity

InGaAs

An assessment of potential InGaAs detector non-linearity was made by comparing opaque or out-of-band spectral regions of atmospheric spectra recorded under typical clear sky conditions with or without a fine mesh attenuator placed in front of the detector, which results in a ~3-fold difference in total incident power. Fig. 4.14 shows the two spectra in first at full scale, then in three regions : at the detector long-wave cut-on just below 4000 cm^{-1} , and at two opacity windows around 5400 cm^{-1} and 7300 cm^{-1} respectively.

Fig. 4.14 : Comparison of InGaAs detector signals in 'dark' spectral regions at the two different total incident power levels.

Table 4.1 lists the mean and RMS of the signal in the three 'dark' regions indicated. In each region, for both spectra, the mean is positive and ~ 0.2 - 0.4 % of the maximum spectrum intensity. The difference

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in mean between the two spectra in each region is also typically an order of magnitude smaller than the RMS ; any InGaAs detector non-linearities therefore appear insignificant at this level.

Spectral region / cm^{-1}	Unattenuated spectrum		Attenuated spectrum	
	Mean	RMS	Mean	RMS
3850-3950	7.11×10^{-5}	6.73×10^{-4}	4.68×10^{-5}	3.31×10^{-4}
5350-5450	6.85×10^{-5}	5.12×10^{-4}	5.38×10^{-5}	3.24×10^{-4}
7275-7375	9.89×10^{-5}	4.35×10^{-4}	6.77×10^{-5}	3.14×10^{-4}

Table 4.1 : Mean and RMS signal levels in 'dark' regions at the two different total incident power levels.

Si detector

A similar assessment for the Si detector cannot be done reliably owing to the lack of wide opacity windows. A qualitative comparison is therefore made. Fig. 4.15, left, shows two Si detector spectra recorded at contrasting though typical air masses, differing by a factor ~ 2 in total incident power.

Fig. 4.15 : Left, Si detector spectra recorded at differing incident power levels. Right, Two narrow opacity windows in the O_2 A-band spectrum illustrating the Si detector behaviour under conditions of complete atmospheric opacity.

Fig. 4.15, right, shows two microwindows in the region of the O_2 A-band absorption, to illustrate the detector behaviour in regions of complete atmospheric opacity, at 13138.25 and 13156.5 cm^{-1} respectively. Without making a quantitative analysis, it appears that any non-linearity effects are not significant under typical recording conditions.

5. Installation conformance to norms

Section 5 illustrates how the Harwell site's installation conforms to what is understood to be typical or normative performance.

5.1. Spectra SNR

Figs. 5.1 and 5.2 show the data of Fig. 4.1 enlarged in the regions of the CO_2 $1.6 \mu\text{m}$ band (InGaAs detector) and the O_2 A-band (Si detector) respectively, with an indication of the SNR in each region. The SNR for the InGaAs and Si spectra are slightly smaller and slightly larger than the values understood to be typical for other TCCON sites, as listed in Table 3.2.

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Fig. 5.1: The InGaAs spectrum in the region of the CO₂ 1.6 μm band recorded on 4th November 2020.

Fig. 5.2: The Si spectrum in the region of the O₂ A- band recorded on 4th November 2020.

5.2. Detector coupling

The Harwell instrument uses DC coupling for acquisition of atmospheric spectra with a pre-amplifier gain of 1 for both Si and InGaAs detectors. The detectors are currently used in AC mode, with a gain of 10 for the InGaAs, when recording HCl spectra in order to increase dynamic range and achieve the requisite spectral SNR in as reasonable time. We believe there may be excess noise in the InGaAs detection chain, and are in contact with Bruker to clarify. When the identified excess noise is suppressed, we plan to revert to DC coupling for both atmospheric transmission and HCl gas cell measurements.

5.3. IFS entrance stop aperture

A 1-mm diameter entrance stop is used for both solar and HCl spectral acquisitions.

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5.4. Nyquist frequency & spectral folding

The Harwell instrument is operated in the ambient atmosphere. Even though, the Nyquist frequency is calculated from the frequency of the HeNe laser in vacuum, yielding 15898 cm^{-1} , as both the spectra and the HeNe laser are recorded under the same conditions, therefore refractive index contribution cancels out. There is sufficient solar radiation above the desired Nyquist frequency for spectral artefacts to be generated by aliasing as seen in the spectra shown in blue and red in Fig. 5.3. A Thorlabs FGL665 long-pass filter (50% transmission @ 665 nm) is used to prevent aliasing of long-wave visible radiation into the region below 15803 cm^{-1} . The effect of the filter is shown in the spectrum in green.

Fig. 5.3: The transmission of the FGL665 anti-aliasing filter and its effect on the Si detector spectrum.

5.5. Scanner velocity

The Harwell instrument uses a 10 kHz scanner 'velocity', being the default recommended by Bruker for the Si and InGaAs detectors.

5.6. High- and low-pass amplifier filters

A low-pass filter bandwidth of 10 kHz is set for both atmospheric spectrum acquisition in DC mode and HCl spectra in AC mode, to match the scanner 'velocity'. In DC mode for atmospheric spectrum acquisition, the high-pass filter is bypassed.

5.7. Acquisition time

Spectra are acquired as individual forward-backward scan cycles. At 10 kHz scanner 'velocity' and 0.02 cm^{-1} resolution, the scan time per forward-backward interferogram pair is $\sim 150\text{ s}$.

5.8. Phase correction

The phase correction length used is equivalent to 1 cm^{-1} resolution.

6. Retrieved columns

Atmospheric transmission spectrum acquisition over the previous 6 months (October 2020 – March 2021) has focused on days of settled weather with largely clear skies for the major part of each day, in order to

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assess stability of performance over a range of solar angles (if possible bracketing local noon) and atmospheric conditions. The full data set consists of a total of 17 days' data.

6.1. Spectral fits

Retrievals were carried out using I2S, GGG2020, the site-specific GEOS files made available by Caltech TCCON and the ground-level meteorological data logged on site. The data presented have not yet been processed using the measured ILS, nor have they been using the HCl scaling factors or any other correction factors. Figs. 6.1(a) and 6.1(b) show illustrative fits to the spectra of more recent data, from 14th June 2021, for the 6220 cm⁻¹ window of CO₂ and the 7885 cm⁻¹ window of O₂.

Fig. 6.1(a) : Spectrum and fit for the 6220 cm⁻¹ CO₂ region to data recorded around 07:30 GMT on 14th June 2021.

Fig. 6.1(b) : Spectrum and fit for the 7885 cm⁻¹ O₂ region to data recorded around 07:30 GMT on 14th June 2021.

The remainder of this section presents four sets of data to illustrate the level of performance achieved and possible remaining shortcomings.

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6.2. *Selected species over single day, with flags*

Figure 6.2 shows the retrieved column VMRs of xLuft, xH₂O, xN₂O, xCH₄ and xCO₂ together with the QC flag for 27th February 2021. The scatter of xLuft is well within expectation ($\pm 1\%$) but it seems affected by a systematic slight positive bias of ~ 0.005 compared to the expected value of 1 within the TCCON community, which may possibly be partially addressed via the air mass independent correction factor. Full data on xLuft are shown in Section 6.4.

Fig. 6.2: Retrieved column VMRs for selected species from 27th February 2021 with the flag associated with each retrieval.

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6.3. xCO_2 , xCH_4 , xN_2O and xCO for each day of the data set

Figs. 6.3(a) – (c) and 6.4(a) – (c) show the retrieved column VMRs xCO_2 , xCH_4 , N_2O and CO for each of the 17 days between September 2020 and March 2021 on which spectra were recorded, filtered to remove QC-flagged data whose FVSI exceeds 5%. Retrievals from ‘forward’ and ‘backward’ interferometer scans are shown in black and red respectively ; here ‘forward’ refers to the first of each scan pair, in which the IFS mirror moved from close to the ZPD position towards maximum OPD.

Fig. 6.3(a) : xCO₂ and xCH₄ retrievals in the period September-November 2020.

Fig. 6.3(b) : xCO₂ and xCH₄ retrievals in the period November-December 2020.

Fig. 6.3(c) : xCO₂ and xCH₄ retrievals in the period January-March 2021.

Fig. 6.4(a) : xN₂O and xCO retrievals in the period September-November 2020.

Fig. 6.4(b) : xN₂O and xCO retrievals in the period November-December 2020.

Fig. 6.4(c) : xN₂O and xCO retrievals in the period January-March 2021. Long-term variation of xCO₂ & xCH₄

6.4. Long-term variation of xCO₂ & xCH₄

Fig. 6.5 shows the data of Figs. 6.3(a)-(c) plotted against time of year to illustrate the variability of xCO₂ and xCH₄ over the 6 months spanned by the data. The trend in xCO₂ from ~ 415 ppm in September to ~ 425 ppm in early March is consistent with the seasonal variation expected for a northern mid-latitude site such as Harwell. The pattern in xCH₄ is more complex, and at the Harwell site is likely to be driven by agricultural land use patterns.

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Fig. 6.5: Variation of xCO₂ and xCH₄ retrievals over the six-month span of available data.

6.5. Forward-backward bias

As noted in Section 6.1, there appears to be a consistent systematic small positive overall bias in xLuft compared to the expected value of 1. The day-to-day variability of the bias is illustrated in Fig. 6.6, in which the mean and RMS of xLuft are shown for each day in the data set. The mean of the daily bias from the ideal value of 1 is 0.0023 ± 0.0014 .

Fig. 6.6 : Mean and RMS of xLuft evaluated daily over the period September 2020 – March 2021.

Retrievals may also show a bias in xLuft between interferograms recorded on the backward compared to the forward scan. The effect is seen for the full data set in Fig. 6.7, which shows xLuft as a function of time of day and of solar zenith angle, segregated into forward (black) and backward (red) scans, with the daily median bias subtracted from each day's data to remove potential slight day-to-day bias. The forward-backward bias is most noticeable at the higher solar zenith angles, where it amounts to ~ 1%. However, the effect is confined approximately to the three months around the winter solstice, and is not an effect dependent solely on the solar zenith angle. As an example, Fig. 6.8 shows the xLuft values for 24th December 2020 and 3rd March 2021, in which the forward-backward bias seen for the December data is not replicated for the March data at similar solar zenith angles early in the day. The origin of this bias will be investigated in the next phase of the TCCON station development.

Fig. 6.7: Bias in xLuft (corrected for potential daily bias) of spectra obtained from forward (black) and backward (red) interferometer scans, shown as a function of solar zenith angle (top) and time of day (bottom).

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Fig. 6.8: Forward-backward bias : xLuft of spectra obtained from forward (black) and backward (red) interferometer scans, shown as a function of solar zenith angle, for data at and away from the winter solstice.

7. Forward look

This report reviews the current status of the Harwell prospective site and aims to solicit feedback and comments from the community and start the accreditation process. In the near future, providing appropriate support from our funding bodies, we will endeavour to:

- Continue routine measurements to generate a longer dataset as far as manual operation and available funding allows,
- Move the facility to a new laboratory providing a much improved field of view (rooftop solar tracker),
- Develop the site automation and reliability to increase the volume of data produced,
- Consolidate the processor and data analysis,
- Start planning for site calibration.

8. Acknowledgements

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